

ФИЛИАЛ РОССИЙСКОГО
ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОГО
УНИВЕРСИТЕТА НЕФТИ И ГАЗА
(СНИУ) ИМЕНИ И.М. ГУБКИНА

ISSN 2181-1482

DOI JOURNAL 10.26739/2181-1482

ИННОВАЦИИ В НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ ОТРАСЛИ

ТОМ 4, НОМЕР 1

INNOVATION IN THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 1

ТАШКЕНТ-2023

ИННОВАЦИИ В НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ ОТРАСЛИ INNOVATION IN THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY

№1 (2023) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-1482-2023-1>

Главный редактор | Chief Editor:

МАГРУПОВ АБДУЛЛА МАХМУДОВИЧ
заместитель директора – исполнительный директор
Филиала Российского государственного университета
нефти и газа (НИУ) имени И.М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте

Технический редактор | Technical Editor:

МАХМУДОВА ШАХНОЗА АБДУВАЛИЕВНА
Заведующий кафедрой «Общепрофессиональные
дисциплины» Филиала Российского государственного
университета нефти и газа (НИУ) имени И.М. Губкина в
г. Ташкенте

РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ СОВЕТ ЖУРНАЛ ИННОВАЦИИ В НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ ОТРАСЛИ EDITORIAL BOARD OF THE JOURNAL INNOVATION IN THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY

МИРСАЙТОВ МИРЗИЁД МИРОЗОДОВИЧ

кандидат технических наук,
заместитель директора по научным работам
и инновациям Филиала Российского
государственного университета нефти и газа (НИУ)
имени И.М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте

ХАИРОВА ДИНАРА РИМОВНА

кандидат экономических наук,
профессор кафедры
"Экономика нефти и газа" Филиала
Российского государственного
университета нефти и газа (НИУ) имени
И.М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте

КАДЫРБЕКОВА ДУРДОНА ХИКМАТУЛЛАЕВНА

доктор философии (PhD) по филологическим
наукам, доцент кафедры
"Иностранные языки Филиала
Российского государственного
университета нефти и газа (НИУ)
имени И.М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте

ХАШАЕВ МУСЛИМ МУСАГИТОВИЧ

доктор философии (PhD), доцент
отделения «Физика, электротехника и
теплотехника» Филиала Российского
государственного университета нефти и газа
(НИУ) имени И.М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте

АКРАМОВ БАХШИЛЛО ШАФИЕВИЧ

кандидат технических наук, профессор
отделения разработки нефтяных, газовых
и газоконденсатных месторождений Филиала
Российского государственного университета нефти
и газа (НИУ) имени И.М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте

ГАФУРОВ КАМОЛ НУРИЛХАКОВИЧ

кандидат экономических наук, Заместитель
директора по учебной работе Филиала Российского
Государственного Университета нефти и газа (НИУ) им.
И.М.Губкина в г. Ташкенте

МИРСОЛИЕВА МУХАББАТХОН ТУХТАСИНОВНА

первый заместитель директора по вопросам молодёжи и
духовно-просветительской работе Филиала Российского
государственного университета нефти и газа (НИУ)
имени И.М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте

НУРАЛИЕВ АЛМУХАН КАЛПАКБАЕВИЧ

кандидат технических наук, доцент
Ташкентского Государственного
технического университета
имени И.А.Каримова

ГЛЕБОВА ЕЛЕНА ВИТАЛЬЕВНА

доктор технических наук,
профессор, заведующая кафедрой
Промышленной безопасности
и охраны окружающей среды
Российского государственного
университета нефти и газа
(НИУ) имени И. М. Губкина (г. Москва)

АЗИМОВ ДИЛМУРОД

доктор технических наук (DSc), профессор
Гавайского университета в Манао (США)

ЭШМАТОВ АЛИМЖОН ХАСАНОВИЧ

PhD, профессор факультета
«Математика и статистика»
Университета Толедо (США)

DESIGN-PAГEMAKER | ДИЗАЙН - ВЕРСТКА: ХУРШИД МИРЗАХМЕДОВ

КОНТАКТ РЕДАКЦИЙ ЖУРНАЛОВ. WWW.TADQIQOT.UZ

ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

EDITORIAL STAFF OF THE JOURNALS OF WWW.TADQIQOT.UZ

Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

1. Отто О.Э., Зиямахомедова Н.Ф.

ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ВОДОРОДНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН \ PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE HYDROGEN ECONOMY IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN \ ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИДА ВОДОРОД ИҚТИСОДИЁТИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ ИСТИҚБОЛЛАРИ.....5

2. Ахмедова Ш.К.

ЭФФЕКТИВНЫЕ ФОРМЫ ВНЕДРЕНИЯ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ МЕТОДОВ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ И УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЕМ НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА \ EFFECTIVE FORMS OF INTRODUCING INNOVATIVE METHODS OF ORGANIZING AND MANAGING AN ENTERPRISE IN THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY OF UZBEKISTAN \ O‘ZBEKISTON NEFT-GAZ SANOA TIDA KORXONANI TASHKIL ETISH VA BOSHQARISHNING INNOVACION USULLARINI YOQISHNING SAMARALI SHAKLLARI.....11

3. Махмуджонов М.М., Матякубова П.М., Кодирова Ш.А.

АНАЛИЗ МЕТРОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИК ГАЗОАНАЛИЗАТОРОВ И МЕТРОЛОГИЧЕСКОЕ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЕ ФИЗИКО-ХИМИЧЕСКИХ ИЗМЕРЕНИЙ \ ANALYSIS OF METROLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF GAS ANALYZERS AND METROLOGICAL SUPPORT OF PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL MEASUREMENTS \ ФИЗИК-КИМЁВИЙ ЎЛЧАШЛАРИНИНГ МЕТРОЛОГИК ТАЪМИНОТИ ВА ГАЗ НАЛИЗАТОРЛАРИНИНГ МЕТРОЛОГИК ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКАЛАРИНИНГ ТАҲЛИЛИ...17

4. Вассер П.Н., Кадирбекова Д.Х.

НОВЫЙ ПОДХОД К ИЗУЧЕНИЮ ЯЗЫКА НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ СПЕЦИАЛЬНОСТИ \ NEW APPROACH OF LEARNING SPECIALISED LANGUAGE OF OIL AND GAS \ NEFT VA GAS SOHASI TILINI URGANISHDA YANGI YONDASHUV.....24

5. Скулкова И.Н., Абдурахманов Р.А.

МЕДИЦИНСКИЕ РЕКОМЕНДАЦИИ И ПРОТИВОПОКАЗАНИЯ ПРИ ЗАНЯТИЯХ ФИЗИЧЕСКИМИ УПРАЖНЕНИЯМИ И ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ДРУГИХ СРЕДСТВ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ ПРИ МИОПИИ \ JISMONIY MASHQLAR PAYTIDA TIBBIY TAVSIYALAR VA KONTRENDIKACIYALAR VA MIYORI UCHUN BOSHQA JISMONIY MADANIYAT VOSITALARIDAN FOYDALANISH \ MEDICAL RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONTRAINDICATIONS FOR PHYSICAL EXERCISES AND THE USE OF OTHER MEANS OF PHYSICAL CULTURE IN MYOPIA.....30

6. Жабборов С.С., Мамаджанов Э.У.

ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ МЕТОДА БУРЕНИЯ С УПРАВЛЯЕМЫМ ДАВЛЕНИЕМ \ APPLICATION OF THE PRESSURE-CONTROLLED DRILLING METHOD \ BOSHQARILADIGAN BO 'ZIMLI BURG' ULLASH USULINI QO 'LLASH.....34

7. Мусаева Ф.М.

ВАЖНОСТЬ АНАЛИЗА ПОТРЕБНОСТЕЙ СТУДЕНТОВ НЕФТЕГАЗОВОГО ВУЗА ПРИ СОЗДАНИИ УЧЕБНЫХ МАТЕРИАЛОВ \ IMPORTANCE OF NEED ANALYSIS IN CREATING TEACHING MATERIALS FOR OIL AND GAS STUDENTS \ NEFT VA GAZ UNIVERSITETI TALABALARI UCHUN O'QUV MATERIALLARINI YARATISHDA ENTIYOJ TAHLILINING AHAMIYATI.....39

8. Алимов М.А., Вохидов О.Ф.

ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ДАТЧИКА ХОЛЛА ДЛЯ ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ КОЛИЧЕСТВА ПРИМЕСИ, СОДЕРЖАЩЕЙСЯ В ФЛЮИДАХ И НАХОДЯЩЕЙСЯ В ПЛАСТЕ \ APPLICATIONS OF THE HALL SENSOR TO DETERMINE THE AMOUNT \ OF IMPURITIES IN THE OIL IN THE RESERVOIR \ N YER OSTI QATLAMLARIDA JOYLASHGAN UGLEVODORODLAR TARKIBIDAGI YOT ELEMENTLARNING MIQDORINI ANIQLASHDA HOLL DATCHIKLARIDAN FOYDALANISH.....43

9. Маджитова О.М.

ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ НА ЗАНЯТИЯХ ПО АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ ДЛЯ СТУДЕНТОВ НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ ОТРАСЛИ \ THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING TECHNOLOGY IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE CLASSROOMS FOR STUDENTS OIL AND GAS \ NEFT VA GAZ SOHASI TALABALARINING INGLIZ TILI DARSLARIDA TEXNOLOGIYADAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGI.....48

10. Усманова А.А., Туймуродова Н.М.,

ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНЫХ НАВЫКОВ И УРОВНЯ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЙ СТУДЕНТОВ ДЛЯ НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ ОТРАСЛИ \ FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL SKILLS AND THE LEVEL OF COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS FOR THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY \ ТАЛАБАЛАРИНИНГ НЕФТ ВА ГАЗ САНОАТИ УЧУН КАСБИЙ КЎНИКМАЛАРИНИ ВА МАЛАКА ДАРАЖАСИНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ.....57

**ТЕЗИСЫ ПОБЕДИТЕЛЕЙ СТУДЕНЧЕСКОЙ
НАУЧНОЙ КОНФЕРЕНЦИИ "НЕФТЬ И ГАЗ -2023"**

1. Забарова Д.Т., Гуляев Д.Т.

КОМПЛЕКСНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ КОНТРОЛЯ КАЧЕСТВА ЦЕМЕНТИРОВАНИЯ И ТЕХНИЧЕСКОГО СОСТОЯНИЯ ОБСАЖЕННОГО СТВОЛА СКВАЖИНЫ \ OMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS OF CEMENTING QUALITY CONTROL AND THE TECHNICAL CONDITION OF A CASED WELLBORE.....62

2. Омонова Ф.Б., Мамарозиков Т.У.

МАГНИТНАЯ РАЗВЕДКА КАК ИНСТРУМЕНТ ДЛЯ ОБНАРУЖЕНИЯ ПОТЕНЦИАЛЬНЫХ АРХЕОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ОБЪЕКТОВ НА ЭТАПЕ ПОИСКОВЫХ РАБОТ \ MAGNETIC PROSPECTING AS A TOOL FOR DETECTING POTENTIAL ARCHAEOLOGICAL SITES DURING THE SEARCH PHASE.....65

3. Отажонов Ш.Х., Мамарозиков Т.У.

ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ МЕТОДА ГРУППИРОВАНИЯ СЕЙСМОПРИЕМНИКОВ ДЛЯ ПОДАВЛЕНИЯ ПОВЕРХНОСТНОЙ ВОЛНЫ \ APPLICATION OF GEOPHONE GROUPING METHOD FOR SURFACE WAVE SUPPRESSION.....68

4. Наримов Д.Ш., Акрамов Б.Ш., Рябов С.С.

ВЫБОР ОПТИМАЛЬНОГО СПОСОБА ЭКСПЛУАТАЦИИ ДОБЫЧИ НЕФТИ В УСЛОВИЯХ ДЕФИЦИТА ЭЛЕКТРОЭНЕРГИИ \ CHOOSING THE OPTIMAL WAY TO OPERATE OIL PRODUCTION IN CONDITIONS OF ELECTRICITY SHORTAGE.....70

5. Добычина С.О., Рябов С.С.

ОБЗОР ВОЛОКОННО-ОПТИЧЕСКИХ ДАТЧИКОВ ДЛЯ ИЗМЕРЕНИЯ ТЕМПЕРАТУРЫ В НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ ОТРАСЛИ \ OVERVIEW OF FIBER OPTIC SENSORS FOR TEMPERATURE MEASUREMENT IN THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY.....72

6. Рахимов С.Н., Ахмедов М.М.

ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКОГО СЕКТОРА УЗБЕКИСТАНА ПУТЕМ ВНЕДРЕНИЯ ВОЗОБНОВЛЯЕМЫХ ИСТОЧНИКОВ ЭНЕРГИИ И ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ИНДИВИДУАЛЬНОЙ СИСТЕМЫ ЭНЕРГООБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ \ OPTIMIZATION OF THE ENERGY SECTOR OF UZBEKISTAN THROUGH INTRODUCING RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES AND THE USE OF AN INDIVIDUAL ENERGY SUPPLY SYSTEM.....74

7. Жабборов С.С., Мамаджанов Э.У.

ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ БИОПОЛИМЕРНЫХ МИКРОСФЕР В МЕСТОРОЖДЕНИЯХ УЗБЕКИСТАНА \ THE POSSIBILITY OF USING BIOPOLYMER MICROSPHERES IN THE FIELDS OF UZBEKISTAN.....77

Маджитова О.М.Филиал РГУ нефти и газа (НИУ)
имени И.М.Губкина в г.Ташкенте,
старший преподаватель**ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ НА ЗАНЯТИЯХ ПО
АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ ДЛЯ СТУДЕНТОВ НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ ОТРАСЛИ** <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7994345>**АННОТАЦИЯ**

Во многих развитых странах признали необходимость и ценность цифровых технологий в изучении языков. Данная статья основана на использовании информационных и коммуникационных технологий (ИКТ) в образовании. Благодаря этой инициативе интерактивное мультимедийное программное обеспечение на основе национальной учебной программы по английскому языку было разработано и апробировано в различных направлениях филиала РГУ нефти и газа им. И.М. Губкина в г.Ташкенте. Результаты подхода показали, что использование аудиовизуального контента имеет большой потенциал для улучшения и продвижения интерактивных языковых занятий. Однако успех педагогического подхода зависит от того, как технология разработана и реализована, и как можно организовать распространение рассмотренного метода учителям при обучении студентов нефтегазовой отрасли.

Ключевые слова: ИКТ в образовании, интерактивный класс, коммуникативное обучение языку, аудиовизуальный учебный материал.

Madjitova O.M.Branch of the Gubkin Russian State
University of Oil and Gas (NIU)
in Tashkent, senior lecturer**THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING TECHNOLOGY IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE
CLASSROOMS FOR STUDENTS OF OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY****ANNOTATION**

Across the globe, governments of different countries have recognized the importance and value of digital technologies in language learning. This article is based on the using information and communication technology (ICT) in education. Through this initiative, interactive multimedia software based on national curriculum of English were developed and tested in different departments of the branch of RSU of oil and gas named after I.M. Gubkin in Tashkent. The results of the approach showed that the use of audio-visual content has strong potential for enhancing and promoting

interactive language classes. However, the success of the program depends on how the technology is designed and implemented and how the teachers are trained to use it.

Keywords: ICT in education, interactive classroom, communicative language teaching, audio-visual classroom material.

Majitova O. M.

I. M. Gubkin nomidagi Rossiya davlat neft va gaz universitetining (NIU) Toshkent shahridagi filiali, katta o'qituvchi

NEFT VA GAZ SOHASI TALABALARI UCHUN INGLIZ TILI DARSLARIDA TEKNOLOGIYADAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ko'pgina rivojlangan davlatlar til o'rganishda raqamli texnologiyalarning zarurligi va ahamiyatini tan olgan. Ushbu maqola ta'limda axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalaridan (AKT) foydalanishga asoslangan. Ushbu tashabbus tufayli Gubkin nomidagi Rossiya davlat neft va gaz universiteti filialining turli yo'nalishlarida ingliz tili bo'yicha milliy o'quv dasturi asosida interaktiv multimedia dasturlari ishlab chiqildi va sinovdan o'tkazildi. Yondashuv natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, audiovizual kontentdan foydalanish interaktiv til darslarini takomillashtirish va rivojlantirish uchun katta imkoniyatlarga ega. Biroq, pedagogik yondashuvning muvaffaqiyati texnologiyaning qanday ishlab chiqilishi va amalga oshirilishi, neft va gaz sanoati talabalariga dars berishda ko'rib chiqilgan usulni o'qituvchilarga tarqatishni qanday tashkil qilish mumkinligiga ham bog'liq.

Kalit so'zlar: Ta'limda AKT, interfaol sinf, kommunikativ tillarni o'rgatish, audiovizual o'quv materiallari.

Introduction. The field of language education is ever changing. Today's language classrooms are vastly different from that of the mid - to late- 20th century (Eaton, 2010). The focus on language education in the 21st century is no longer on grammar, memorization, and learning from rote, but rather using language and cultural knowledge as a means to communicate and connect to others around the globe (Eaton, 2010). Traditional notions of education are giving way to newer, more innovative ways of thinking about how we learn, teach, and acquire knowledge. The American Council on the Teaching of Foreign Language (ACTFL, 2013) noted that technology has been used to both assist and enhance language learning. It is now rare to find a language class that does not use some form of technology.

The government of Uzbekistan has taken various measures to use technology to improve and modernize the overall education system. The approach of using ICT in English learning classes of the oil and gas sphere students was implemented in 5 groups in the university of RSU of oil and gas named after I.M. Gubkin in Tashkent.

The current research was conducted to determine the effectiveness of the audiovisual materials from internet resources. The key question that triggered to closely monitor and record the changes was, "What are the benefits and challenges of using supplementary audiovisual material in the English lessons?" This paper is based on the research findings of a one-semester (2022-2023) program implementation experience in UGF (21-16), UGI (22-08, 21-15), URG (22-01, 21-03) groups.

Background and Rationale of the Research. A situation analysis was conducted prior to implementing the approach with five groups to gather baseline data. The focus of the survey was to analyze the students' annual semester results in English teaching practices in the university. Findings (Table 1) indicated that, in English, there was a consistent decline in performances across all groups from first year students and most of the students in these groups failed English. Apart from second year students, student performance in English decreased slightly when they went on to next semesters. The marks degraded abruptly from semester 2 to semester 3 for all the studied groups.

Thus, approach project developed the university groups and is being carried on.

Table 1

Scores in English Obtained from the five groups as of 2022-2023

Term	group 1	group 2	group 3	group 4	group 5
Semester I	58	53	24	53	38
Semester II	70	61	42	61	33

Source: Situation Analysis Report (2022).

To enhance the learning of students, the communicative language teaching (CLT) approach in English language classes was introduced. This approach requires interactive classroom activities and the integration of the four language skills of reading, writing, listening, and speaking (Sharif, 2012). Most groups however do not have the possibility to appropriately implement the CLT approach. As a result the approach strongly suggests the availability and use of audiovisual materials for teaching English lessons. To support the recommendation, to improve basic pedagogy of English through infusing technology in the groups takes long period to be accepted.

Research Questions. What are the benefits and challenges of using supplementary audiovisual material in the English lessons of oil and gas specialized institutions? That was the key question that guided the ICT approach to do the research. The research was developed to closely monitor and record changes that occurred in groups resulting from the use of supplementary audiovisual material of English. The major objectives of the analysis were to determine: ^{1 2 3 4}

1. What effects does the use of supplementary audiovisual material have on students' engagement in English language learning?
2. How are classroom activities conducted in English classes, specifically classes using the CLT approaches, where teachers use the supplementary audiovisual material?
3. Given the experiences of one-year implementation, what are the prospects for the scale-up and sustainability of the initiative?
4. What are the opportunities and challenges of taking the program to scale through collaboration with the government?

Literature Review. It was observed by Warschauer (2000) that the style of language teaching has changed over the years. Warschauer noted that virtually every type of language teaching has had its own supporting technologies. For instance, teachers who followed the grammar translation method (i.e., where the teacher explained the grammatical rules and the students performed the translations) used the technology of the blackboard. This was merely a one-way transmission of information. Later the blackboard was replaced with the overhead projector, which allowed for a teacher dominated learning approach. In the 1970's and the 1980's, university language classes comprised of mandatory sessions in the audio labs. In these labs students would enter at a designated time and perform repetition drills on computers (Warschauer, 2000). The main purpose of the language lab was for students to gain auditory exposure to the language they were studying. The audio lab proved to be quite innovative in the mid-twentieth century since it provided students with exposure to the voice of a native speaker. At that time, students had far fewer opportunities to travel. Whether in the lab or in the classroom, repetitive drills that emphasized technology only and ignored communication achieved poor results. Finally, in the 1980s and 1990s, the field saw a shift towards CLT to emphasize student engagement

in authentic and meaningful interactions (Warschauer, 2000).

Advantages of Using Technologies in the Language Classroom

The review of recent research on technology-supported language learning reveals a number of interesting points. For example, Zhao (2013) conducted a study to assess the potential of technology for improving language education. The review found that existing literature on the effectiveness of technology use in language education is very limited in four aspects:

- 1) the number of systematic, well-designed empirical evaluative studies of the effects of technology uses in language learning is very small;
- 2) the settings of instruction where the studies were conducted were limited to higher education and adult learners;
- 3) the languages studied were limited to common foreign languages and English as a foreign or second language; and
- 4) the experiments were often short-term and focused on one or two aspects of language learning (e.g., vocabulary or grammar).

Nevertheless, the limited number of studies indicates a pattern of positive effects. Most studies found technology-supported language learning is at least as effective as human teachers, if not more so.

Hennessy (2005) noted the introduction of ICTs could act as a catalyst in stimulating teachers and pupils to work in new ways. Teacher-pupil and peer discussion, exploration, analysis and reflection, probing, assistance, and feedback characterize these. Hennessy noted that as students become more autonomous, teachers feel that they should encourage and support pupils in acting and thinking independently. Warschauer (2000) described two distinct perspectives about how to integrate technology into the classroom. First, in the cognitive approach learners get the opportunity to maximize their exposure to language in a meaningful context and construct their own individual knowledge. Examples of these types of technologies include text-reconstruction software and multimedia simulation software. Multimedia simulation software allows learners to enter into computerized micro worlds with exposure to language and culture in a meaningful audio-visual context. The best of these programs allow learners a good deal of control and interactivity so they can better manipulate their linguistic input. Second, the social approach emphasizes the social aspect of language acquisition where learning a language is viewed as a process of socialization. From this perspective, students need to be given opportunities for authentic social interactions to practice real life skills. This can be achieved through student collaboration on authentic tasks and projects.

Eaton (2010) found that computer-based communication is a beneficial feature for language learning. Computer-assisted discussion tend to feature more equal participation than face to-face discussion. Teachers or a few outspoken students are less likely to dominate the floor, resulting in class discussions that are more collaborative. Zhao (2013) supported this view by stating that access and exposure to engaging, authentic, and comprehensible yet demanding materials in the target language is essential for successful language learning.

Ke (2009) suggested that instructional games tend to nurture higher order thinking such as planning and reasoning. Ke's conclusion is drawn from studies that looked into cognitive learning outcomes in the areas of basic motor skills, descriptive knowledge, conceptual knowledge, problem solving, and general cognitive strategies. Also, instructional computer games seem to facilitate motivation across different learner groups and learning situations. These findings are based on studies that looked at effective learning outcomes, involving self-efficacy, attitudes toward subject content learning, and effective feedback toward game use, as well as looking at continuing motivation.

Considering the above review of literature, technology in the primary school classrooms with the hope of improving language teaching and learning practices has been introduced. To determine the effects of the introduction of technology in oil and gas institutions, I conducted this research. The following section provides a brief description of the ICT approach project.

The ICT approach project. The ICT in education project has taken the challenge to improve classroom pedagogy through training teachers how to utilize ICTs to develop subject-based content. To promote the CLT approach in the English lessons, I tried to introduced innovative supplementary classroom teaching learning tools in the university groups by developing the supplementary classroom teaching e-content for 5 groups, English, based on the national authentic materials, taken from internet. It is expected that the use of e-content with 5 groups would make a positive impact on the results of completion exam. The interactive audiovisual program is being used as a supplementary classroom teaching material in the multimedia classrooms

(classroom equipped with a laptop and a monitor). The developed content is implemented in 5 university groups. The project covers 64 810 students.

Supplementary e-content

The supplementary e-content consists of flash based interactive lessons that were developed to align with the national authentic materials and textbooks published at Oxford on petroleum specialty. Through delivering the supplementary e-content, teachers will be able to take full advantage of the potential of technology to enhance student learning. The supplementary audiovisual material of the groups was fully integrated into the existing educational processes. The audiovisual materials of the ICT project were developed so that teachers could learn new pedagogical skills by integrating four language skills (listening, speaking, reading, and writing) using interactive tasks. The audiovisual materials were carefully crafted with skills integrated in teaching and activities, so that learners practiced language skills through a variety of engaging activities.

In the dual screen option as shown on Figure 1, two different screens were run simultaneously in the classroom: one for the teacher and the other for the students. The dual screen of the software brought in a unique dimension to this software. The teachers' section was shown on the laptop and the students' section was shown on the monitor. The content of both the screens were the same, with the exception that the teachers' screen included teacher's note to guide him/her during the lesson. In order to use the dual screen display, teachers needed to change the computer's display setting to dual screen mode.

Figure 1. Dual Screens in the e-Content with the Teacher's Note

Teacher's Note (in the Software)

The teacher's note provided guidance to teachers about how the instruction should be conducted in the classroom. It focused on how the interaction with the students should be initiated. The teachers' note provided detailed direction to the teachers about how to carry out the teaching of the materials along with samples of language they may use during interactions with students.

Method. The methodology of this action research is being designed to document the observable changes in the English language groups in the university of oil and gas resulting from the use of audiovisual materials as supplementary teaching aids. Between November and March of 2022-2023, I have been collecting the following data:

- Semester results for students in ICT and non-ICT groups
- Focus group discussion with students

Comparison of semester results

To determine the impact of the use of content on students' learning, the English test scores on students' semester tests in January of 2023 are collected. I checked the test answer-scripts, after results from 5 ICT groups were collected and compared them with the results from 4 groups that did not use the supplementary audiovisual content in the classroom.

Focus group discussion with students

The English content was piloted in 5 groups with me. After implementing the intervention, three focus group discussions were conducted with the students. Two focus group discussions were conducted with randomly selected students in the ICT groups.

During the beginning of supplementary content implementation, group monitoring was also conducted via questioning students. To determine the effects of supplementary e-content in English classes, I have also observed 3 non-ICT groups where any audiovisual materials were used. See Table 2 below for details.

During these discussions, students provided immediate reflections on the lessons. In addition to observing the lessons I analyzed lesson plans, activity sheets, and samples of student work. The teacher reflection diary was also reviewed.

Table 2. Classroom Observation type

Observation Type	Number of Observations
Classes (e-content)	20
Video Recorded Classes (e-content)	3
Observed Classes (non-ICT)	10

Findings. The findings are based on an analysis of semester test results from both ICT pilot and non-ICT groups, focus group discussion with students, and lesson observations. The findings from two perspectives have been analyzed: 1) Impact on the students' learning outcomes; and 2) Changes in the classroom pedagogy and teacher development. What follows is a summary of the findings from the project.

Effects of Supplementary Audiovisual Materials on Students' English Language Learning

To understand the impact of the innovation on students' learning, students' test scores were collected from their semester final tests held in December 2023. The students' test scores of 5 ICT groups were obtained. For comparison, I also collected test scores of 3 non-ICT groups in the identical departments. As detailed in Table 3, the mark analysis showed a higher achievement for students in ICT approach than students in non-ICT groups.

Table 3. Average Test Scores on the 2022 semester final tests.

Group Type	Average Test Scores
ICT groups	80.87%
Non-ICT groups	65.89%

Note: 8 schools in each group type.

Table 4. E-Content and Student

Students are...	Females	Males	Percentage
more attentive and focused in English class	6	11	78.57
learning the usage of correct pronunciation	6	9	71.43
more inclined towards speaking English in the classroom	4	11	64.29
building vocabulary	8	9	85.71
learning concepts of English language quickly and easily	9	11	100.00

Note: 20 students were selected at random out of 5 participating groups.

As shown in Table 4, most teachers found the e-content to be useful for the students. Nearly 79% of the students said they were more attentive and focused in the class when using the e-content. 71% of the students noted that they were learning the usage of correct pronunciation. 64% of students reported that they were eager to speak English. 86% of the students indicated that students showed an increase in vocabulary abilities. All of the learners indicated that students showed

competency in learning the concepts of English language quickly and easily through use of the e-content.

Emerging. The integration of audiovisual content in the classroom played a positive role in creating learner-oriented classrooms. Through the technology, it was possible to examine students' actions and thinking process. While observing the classes, it was noticed that the questioning skills of students increased. Thus the tool supported students' learning by directing them to useful resources, rephrasing important questions, and providing additional information and answers to their questions.

Applying. The activities in the e-content require teachers to conduct classes by engaging students. The supplementary e-content put emphasis on the speaking skills activities of the textbook. This engage the students in talking more and practicing English more in the classrooms. The introduction of e-content acted as a catalyst and stimulating teachers and students to work in new ways. These were characterized by teacher-student and peer discussion in exploration, analysis, and reflection. The integration of four groups' content in class teaching made the learners' practice reading, writing, speaking, and listening in English for a variety of real and engaging purposes.

Students. The most significant change for students was that the classroom environment became more enjoyable as compared to non-ICT classes. The students were very attentive, excited, and curious in the English classes through use of the e-content. The integration of audiovisual content in the classroom played a positive role in creating learner-oriented classrooms where it was possible to monitor students' actions and thinking processes. While observing the classes, it was noticed that the questioning skills of students' also improved. Thus the approach supported students' learning by directing them to useful resources, helping them rephrase important questions, and providing additional information and answers to their questions.

Challenges and Recommendations. The observation findings and focus group discussions with students indicate that there are some challenges in the use of supplementary audiovisual e-content. The major objective of introducing the supplementary audiovisual e-content was to improve the learning outcomes of all students. While observing the groups, it was noted that I put more focus on completing the e-content rather than focusing on language or grammar. In contrast, in non-ICT groups all students are ensured to memorize the answers or allowed to drill in chorus. Keeping students on task is important for teachers in order to maintain the focus of the lesson. The teachers need more training to use the content effectively and in conjunction with the textbook.

At the same time it was also seen that a group of students remained silent or failed to do the given task. In this way I did not provide attention to the slow learners, it cannot be said that the supplementary e-content successfully reached all students.

Less Time for Lesson Preparation

It was found that sometimes teachers were using the content as a tool without having enough preparation. This was often a result of a lack of facilities for preparation before going to class. In the pilot schools, there was one laptop that was not kept in the classroom during the school hour. Among the project teachers, only three teachers had personal computers. This situation required that teachers to complete their preparation for the lesson after school hours or during their breaks.

Discussion and Recommendations. The groups' observation findings and literature review for this report show that not all the institutions in Uzbekistan and some other countries are familiar with the ICT approach. Although the English textbooks are written in accordance with the ICT approach, rooms are not provided with adequate facilities for students to practice all four language skills. Similarly, teachers are not always familiar with the ICT approach and lack the required competencies in English communication. The ICT pilot not only brought better presentations to students, it may improve teachers' learning of content, thereby improving content presented to students. The supplementary e-content provides opportunity for students and teachers to listen and learn correct pronunciations.

In our society, the opportunities for hearing and speaking English is limited. The non-ICT group observation showed that most of the students followed the grammar translation method. This method did not help students see the value of English, rather, students 'learned' English just to pass

their tests (Sharif, 2012). The lack of required competencies in the English communication skills among teachers also makes the implementation of the ICT approach quite challenging.

The introduction of the audiovisual material supported teachers in effectively applying the ICT approach in the classrooms. The e-content supported students in dialogue practicing, reading, and listening, context-based question and answer tasks, peer checking, drills, games, role-play, drama, interview, brainstorming and performing in pairs or groups. The dual screen option of the developed e-content was found to be the greatest innovation and brought a new dimension to this project. The teachers' section with detailed directions about how to carry out the teaching and learning of the materials in class, along with sample of the actual language that they used for interaction with students, helps teachers better facilitate instruction.

The findings indicate one approach to introducing technology in the language classroom of the government education system in Uzbekistan and highlighted opportunities for further exploration and research.

References:

1. American Council on The Teaching of Foreign Languages (ACTFL). (2013) Role of technology in language learning. Retrieved on 22 November 2014
2. Eaton, S. E. (2010). Global trends in language learning in the twenty-first century. Calgary, Canada: Onate Press.
3. Engida, T., (2011) ICT-enhanced Teacher Development Model, UNESCO International Institute for Capacity Building in Africa (IICBA). Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.
4. Ferdig (Ed.), Handbook of Research on Effective Electronic Gaming in Education (pp. 1-32). Hershey, PA: Information Science Reference. <http://www.actfl.org/news/position-statements/role-technology-language-learning>.
5. from <http://www.actfl.org/news/position-statements/role-technology-language-learning>.
6. Hennessy, S. (2005). Emerging teacher strategies for supporting. Cambridge, UK: University of Cambridge.
7. Kapp, K. M. (2012). The gamification of learning and instruction: Game-based methods and strategies for training and education. San Francisco, CA: John Wiley & Sons.
8. Save the Children. (2015). Mapping ICT in education initiatives in Bangladesh. Dhaka, Bangladesh: Author.
9. Sharif, M. Y. (2012). Communicative approach: An innovative tactic in English language teaching. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 3(4), 64-70.
10. UNESCO. (2012). ICT in primary education analytical survey. Retrieved on 22 November 2014 from <http://iite.unesco.org/pics/publications/en/files/3214707.pdf>.
10. Zhao, Y. (2013). Recent developments in technology and language learning: Literature review and meta-analysis. *CALICO Journal*, 21(1), 7-27.

Усманова А.А.,

Филиала Российского государственного университета нефти и газа (НИУ) имени И.М. Губкина в городе Ташкенте
к.п.н., доцент заведующая кафедрой «Социально-гуманитарные дисциплины» Филиала РГУ нефти и газа

Туймуродова Н.М.,

студентка 2 курса направления «Производственный менеджмент»
Филиала Российского государственного университета нефти и газа (НИУ) имени И.М. Губкина в городе Ташкенте

ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНЫХ НАВЫКОВ И УРОВНЯ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЙ СТУДЕНТОВ ДЛЯ НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ ОТРАСЛИ

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7994349>

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье рассмотрены современные подходы в формировании конкурентоспособных специалистов для нефтегазовой отрасли страны, исследования ученых, посвященных технологиям поэтапной профессиональной подготовки, совершенствованию профессиональных навыков и опыта. Представлены основные критерии эффективности профессионального развития студентов в нефтегазовой отрасли.

Usmanova A.A.,

Branch of the Gubkin Russian State University of Oil and Gas (NRU) in Tashkent,
PhD, Associate Professor, Head of the Department of «Social and Humanitarian Disciplines»

Tuymurodova N.M.,

2nd year student of the direction «Production Management»

FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL SKILLS AND THE LEVEL OF COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS FOR THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY

ANNOTATION

The article considers modern approaches to the formation of competitive specialists for the oil and gas industry of the country, research by scientists devoted to technologies of step-by-step professional training, improvement of professional skills and experience. The main criteria for the effectiveness of professional development of students in the oil and gas industry are presented.

Усманова А.А.,

И.М. Губкин номидаги (МТУ) Россия давлат нефть ва газ университетининг Ташкент шаҳридаги филиали

ФИЛИАЛ РОССИЙСКОГО
ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОГО
УНИВЕРСИТЕТА НЕФТИ И ГАЗА
(НИУ) ИМЕНИ И.М. ГУБКИНА

ИННОВАЦИИ В НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ ОТРАСЛИ

ТОМ 4, НОМЕР 1

INNOVATION IN THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 1

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz

Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz

ООО Тадқиқот город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000